

Micro level differential pulse polarographic determination of zirconium in soil samples

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Abstract : A simple and convenient differential pulse polarographic method is described for the determination of low concentration of zirconium in soil samples. The present study was undertaken keeping in view of the fact that choice of a medium for polarographic investigations in case of zirconium is limited due to its very negative reduction potential. Among different supporting electrolytes investigated for the study of Zr^{IV} at DME, 0.01 M KNO_3 was found most adequate where Zr^{IV} displayed single polarographic wave at a potential of -1.01 V. Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cr^{VI} , Ni^{II} , V^V and Mn^{II} did not interfere. It was observed that on increasing the concentration of zirconium the peak current increased linearly upto a concentration of 2.2 ppm. Limit of determination was observed to be 0.01 ppm.

Keywords : Differential pulse polarography, zirconium, soil samples.

Introduction

It was noticed that direct polarographic methods for determination of zirconium are unsuitable because it has a highly negative reduction potential which is preceded by the hydrogen discharge. The standard electrode potential of zirconium has been reported to be -1.53 V for the reduction reaction : $Zr^{4+} + 4e^- \rightarrow Zr^0$ ($E^0 = -1.53$ V)¹. Therefore several workers have suggested indirect polarographic determination of zirconium. Cozzi² has observed that the reduction wave of Zr in $ZrOCl_2$ solution is very close to that of hydrogen wave but when methylene blue is added the hydrogen wave is displaced and if pH is maintained in between 2.5 and 4.0, a wave corresponding to direct reduction to metallic zirconium is obtained. Many other authors³⁻¹¹ have also described polarographic behaviour of zirconium and other metal ions in different media. The present study was undertaken keeping in view of the fact that choice of a medium for polarographic investigations in case of zirconium is limited due to its very negative reduction potential. Herein, among different supporting electrolytes investigated for the differential pulse polarographic study of Zr^{IV} at DME, 0.01 M KNO_3 was found most adequate for micro level determination of zirconium.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

A microprocessor based pulse polarographic analyzer (Model CL-362) in combination with a drop-timer assembly, all from Elico Limited, Hyderabad, India, was used for polarographic measurements. Current voltage curves were recorded by an Epson printer (Epson-LX-300+II). The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as the working electrode; pulse amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time of pulse, 0.5 s; scan rate, 12 mV/s and charging current compensation, 20%. Potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Platinum wire was used as auxiliary electrode. Polarographic medium employed was 0.01 M KNO_3 .

A Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model UV-108) with a wavelength range of 190-900 nm was also used for sample analysis. Tungsten-halogen deuterium lamp and wide range photomultiplier were used as the light source and detector, respectively. The spectral band width was 0.5 nm.

The pH studies were made by a Systronics digital pH meter (Model-355).

Soil sample preparation :

Soil samples were powdered, dried and leached in an acid mixture of hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid by keeping overnight. It was followed by vigorous shaking and washing. The contents were then finally transferred to a volumetric flask and made upto the requisite volume.

Chemicals :

Chemicals used in this work were of analytical grade purity. Standard solution of zirconium was prepared from zirconium oxychloride octahydrate ($ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$) dissolved in minimum amount of HCl. These solutions were prepared using Milli-Q water (Millipore). Test solutions were deaerated for 20 min by passing purified nitrogen. All of the experiments were carried out in an air-conditioned laboratory where the temperature was maintained at 25 ± 1 °C. Nitrogen was purified by passing the gas through a vanadous chloride scrubbing solution kept in contact with amalgamated zinc to remove traces of oxygen¹².

Results and discussion

Polarographic characteristics :

Zr^{IV} in presence of 0.01 M KNO_3 displayed well-defined single polarographic wave at a potential of -1.01 V (Fig. 1). The plot of E vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ revealed that electroreduction of zirconium(IV) in 0.01 M KNO_3 was irreversible, although waves appeared to be diffusion controlled.

Differential pulse polarographic studies :

Zirconium(IV) showed a sharp DP peak in presence of 0.01 M KNO_3 supporting electrolyte at a potential of -1.01 V as shown in Fig. 2. It was observed that on increasing the concentration of zirconium the peak current increased linearity upto a concentration of 2.2 ppm. Calibration linearity of Zr^{IV} in 0.01 M KNO_3 is shown in Fig. 3.

Interference :

The commonly present metal ions in industrial waste water samples such as copper, lead, cadmium and zinc were tested for their interference during the DPP determination of zirconium. The peak potential of Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were found well-separated from that of zirconium(IV) in 0.01 M KNO_3 . It has been shown in Fig. 4 and peak potentials are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 1. DC Polarogram of zirconium(IV) : (a) Blank solution of 0.01 M KNO_3 , (b) 7×10^{-5} M Zr^{IV} in 0.01 M KNO_3 .

Fig. 2. DP Polarogram of zirconium(IV) : (a) Blank solution of 0.01 M KNO_3 , (b) 1.4 ppm of zirconium(IV) in 0.01 M KNO_3 .

Fig. 3. DP Polarogram of zirconium(IV) at different concentrations in 0.01 M KNO_3 .

Electrochemical data revealed that reduction potential of Zn^{II} in acidic medium occurs at -1.1 V. In our studies and optimizing experimental conditions Zn^{II} shows a DP peak at -1.31 V thus did not interfere in determination of Zr^{IV}. It has been clarified in Fig. 4. Also U^{VI} is a coexisting metal ion and gives a DP peak at -1.26 V in

V^V in determination of Zr^{IV} in 0.01 M KNO₃ are shown by DP Polarogram in Fig. 5 (Table 1).

Limit of determination :

The limit of determination of zirconium in these conditions achieved was 0.01 µg/ml.

Fig. 4. DP Polarogram of Zr^{IV} in presence of Cu^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} in 0.01 M KNO₃. Cu^{II}; Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} = 2 × 10⁻⁴ M; Zr^{IV} = 5.3 × 10⁻⁵ M; Zn^{II} = 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ M.

Table 1. Peak potential of metal ions in 0.01 M KNO₃

Metal ions	-E _p (V) vs SCE
Copper(II)	0.18
Lead(II)	0.35
Cadmium(II)	0.57
Chromium(VI)	0.88
Zirconium(IV)	1.01
Nickel(II)	1.16
Vanadium(V)	1.25
Zinc(II)	1.31
Manganese(II)	1.63

thioglycolic acid with acetate buffer media and also did not interfere in the determination.

Some other metal ions whose reduction potential values are close to that of Zr^{IV} were also studied for interference. These include chromium(VI), nickel(II), vanadium(V) and manganese(II)¹³. DPP studies carried out for monitoring of interference of Cr^{VI}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II} and

Accuracy and precision :

The reproducibility of the method was evaluated by determining zirconium simultaneously in a test solution of known concentration under the optimized experimental conditions. The obtained data were found quantitative with standard deviation of 0.007 (±) at a concentration of 0.1 µg/ml zirconium with a percentage error of 0.5% inferring that method is precise and accurate. It is justified in Table 2.

Analytical applications :

DP polarographic reduction of zirconium(IV) in 0.01 M KNO₃ has been successfully applied for the determination of trace level zirconium in soil samples.

Voltammetric measurement :

The prepared soil samples were taken in polarographic cell with 0.01 M KNO₃ supporting electrolyte. DP polarograms were recorded between -0.8 to -1.4 V and

Fig. 5. (a) DP Polarogram of Cr^{VI}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} in 0.01 M KNO₃, (b) DP polarogram of V^V in 0.01 M KNO₃.

Table 2. Precision and accuracy of DPP determination of zirconium in 0.01 M KNO₃

Zirconium ion				
Present (μg/ml)	Determined ^a (μg/ml)	S.D. (±)	R.S.D (%)	Relative error (%)
0.1	0.099	0.007	6.82	0.5

^aAverage of five determinations.

peak currents were measured at -1.01 V after making blank corrections. The concentrations were determined by standard addition method¹⁴. The results of zirconium determination in various soil samples are summarized in Table 3.

Validation :

The validity of DPP measurements was further estab-

lished by comparing the results with UV-Vis spectrophotometric method. The comparative data are included in Table 4.

Table 3. DPP determination of zirconium(IV) in soil samples

Soil samples ^a	Zr ^{IV} conc. (ppm)
1.	0.5000
2.	0.4541
3.	0.4984
4.	0.4708
Average	0.4808

^aSoil samples were collected from a cement industrial area.
N = 3, No. of replicates.

Table 4. Comparison of results of Zr^{IV} determination by DPP and UV-Vis spectrophotometry

Soil sample	Zr ^{IV} conc. (ppm)	
	DPP	UV-Vis
1	0.5000	0.4808
2	0.4541	0.4340
3	0.4984	0.4760
4	0.4708	0.4580

Conclusion

The proposed DPP method for determination of zirconium is of simple approach, accurate and quantitative in terms of measurement (detection limit = 0.01 µg/ml) and precision (S.D. ± 0.007). The method will be of use in clinical laboratories as the ingestion or inhalation of Zr⁹³, a radioactive isotope, can cause slight increase in likelihood of developing cancer.

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